

Egg-Laying Behavior of *Pheosia albivertex* on *Populus alba* in natural habitat

MOHD HUSSAIN^{1,*} & NASSREEN FATIMA KACHO²

¹Department of Zoology, University of Ladakh, UT Ladakh, India

²SKUAST-K KVK Kargil, UT Ladakh, India

Email: fimkacho898@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4683-8602>

*Corresponding author Email: dr.hussainto168@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6791-4670>

Abstract

This study investigates the egg-laying behavior of the moth *Pheosia albivertex* (Hampson 1983) (Lepidoptera: Notodontidae) on the host plant *Populus alba* (Salicaceae) in its natural habitat in Deyanguchey village of Kargil Ladakh, India. Previously reported findings indicated clustered egg-laying in a controlled environment. Our observations reveal that in the wild, females lay eggs singly, with a maximum of five eggs per leaf. This deviation may be influenced by the availability of suitable oviposition sites.

Key words: Lepidoptera, Moth, Eggs, Trans-Himalaya, Kargil, Ladakh

Introduction

Pheosia albivertex, a species within the family Notodontidae, has recently been identified as an invasive pest on *Populus alba* in Deyanguchey village of Kargil Ladakh, India (Hussain et al. 2024). Prior research documented in a controlled laboratory setting showed females laying eggs in clusters, potentially due to limited leaf availability (Hussain et al. 2024). This study aims to compare egg-laying patterns in the natural habitat to understand the behavioral ecology of this species.

Materials and methods

Field observations were conducted during the peak oviposition period in first week of May 2024 in various *Populus alba* stands across Deyanguchey village of Kargil Ladakh with the Geo location of 34°27'44.88"N, 76°04'20.03"E and 2817m of elevation, above sea level (Fig. 1). Each observation session included inspecting leaves for eggs, noting the number of eggs per leaf, and recording the spatial distribution of egg-laying on the trees. A photograph of the leaf sample was captured by DSLR camera, Canon EOS 1500D.

Figure 1. Study area, Deyanguchey village of Kargil, Ladakh.

Results

Contrary to the clustered egg-laying observed in controlled environments, field observations revealed that *Pheosia albivertex* females lay eggs singly on *Populus alba* leaves. The maximum number of eggs observed on a single leaf was five (Figure 2). This suggests a strategic dispersion likely aimed at reducing intra-species competition and increasing offspring survival rates.

Figure 2. *Pheosia albivertex*; A, Adult male; B, Adult female; C, eggs on the inner surface of the host plant (*Populus alba*).

Discussion

The genus *Pheosia* includes 27 species known for causing defoliation in various host plants, such as *Salix* spp., *Betula* spp., and *Populus* spp. (Schintlmeister and Lai, 2001; ADW: *Pheosia*: Classification, 2023). Hussain et al. (2024) recorded an infestation of *Pheosia albivertex* on *Populus alba* in Deyanguchey village, Kargil, Ladakh, and observed that the moths lay eggs in clusters. Generally, *Pheosia* spp. lay eggs either solitarily or in loose clusters (Dolinskaya, 2016). In the present study, a discrepancy was noted between the clustered egg-laying behavior observed in captivity and the solitary egg deposition seen in the wild for *Pheosia albivertex*. This difference could be attributed to the natural availability of oviposition sites (Hussain et al., 2024). Insects are highly successful animals due to their intelligent oviposition behavior, consistently seeking out the best sites to ensure the survival of their larvae and the completion of the life cycle. Egg-laying behavior in moth species is influenced by many factors, including the availability of food (Cury et al., 2019; Chaudhary et al., 2022). From the present study, it can determine that limited leaf resources in a controlled setting force females to cluster their eggs, whereas in the wild, an abundance of suitable leaves allows for solitary egg deposition. This behaviour of egg laying in *Pheosia albivertex* was observed on *Populus alba* in its natural habitat in Deyanguchey village, Kargil, Ladakh, India, where females laid no more than five eggs per leaf (Figure 2). This behavioral plasticity highlights the adaptability of *Pheosia albivertex* to varying environmental conditions and contributes to a deeper understanding of the reproductive ecology of this invasive pest, informing management practices.

References

- ADW: Pheosia: Classification. 2023. Available at: <http://animaldiversity.org/accounts/Pheosia/classification/> [Date accessed: 7 August 2023].
- Chaudhary, D. D., & Kumar, B. 2022. Oviposition Strategies. In *Reproductive Strategies in Insects*. CRC Press. (pp. 307-322). DOI: 10.1201/9781003043195-15
- Cury, K. M., Prud'homme, B. & Gompel, N. 2019. A short guide to insect oviposition: when, where and how to lay an egg. *Journal of Neurogenetics*, 33(2): 75-89.
- Dolinskaya, I. V. 2016. Key to the species of Ukrainian Notodontid Moths (Lepidoptera, Notodontidae) on the egg characters. *Vestnik zoologii*, 50(6): 517-532. DOI 10.1515/vzoo-2016-0059
- Hussain, M., Kacho, N. F., Shashank, P. R., Ali, M. & Mir, A. H. 2024. First report of an invasive pest, *Pheosia albivertex* (Hampson 1983) (Lepidoptera: Notodontidae) on *Populus alba* (Salicaceae), from Ladakh, India. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Biodiversity*, 17(2024): 321-326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japb.2023.12.007>
- Schintlmeister A, Lai F. C. 2001. New and less known Notodontidae from mainland China. *Neue Entomologische Nachrichten*:66